

ADAPTIVE WINDOW EXCITATION CODING IN LOW-BIT-RATE CELP CODERS

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ABSTRACT

A new paradigm for efficient coding of the fixed-codebook excitation in CELP coders at low-bit rates is presented. In this scheme, the non-zero components of the fixed-codebook excitation are localized to a set of windows whose locations are dependent on the pitch frequency and on the energy contour of a modified residual signal. Highly efficient coding is thus achieved by allocating most of the fixed excitation bits to capture the essential excitation events. The paradigm is validated by computer simulation of a variable-rate speech codec. The performance of the codec is evaluated by informal subjective tests comparing it with TIA standard variable rate speech codecs. The results confirm that the proposed scheme can be used to reproduce speech at average bit rates from 2.3 to 3.4 kbps with very high quality and intelligibility.

1. INTRODUCTION

In conventional code-excited linear prediction (CELP) coding, a signal that is composed of fixed and adaptive codebook (FCB and ACB) components excites an all-pole filter to generate the synthetic speech. Generally, it is assumed that the ACB contributes to the periodic component of the excitation, while the FCB handles the random component. Hence, the original CELP paradigm [7] allowed an FCB excitation that is statistically random and stationary in nature. Recent CELP coders based on multi-pulse codebooks are more effective, but nevertheless assume that the FCB pulses are randomly distributed with uniform pulse density over time. These coders approach toll-quality speech only at bit rates of 6 kbps or higher. At lower rates, their performance suffers because of inadequate encoding of the FCB excitation.

The starting point of our proposal is the observation that the FCB excitation displays strong periodicity and energy localization properties; i.e., there are small (localized) and periodically occurring time intervals where the FCB excitation is most active. This is particularly true in voiced and transient segments. Conventional fixed codebooks based on multi-pulse or random excitation do not exploit this property. We note that in the context of multi-pulse codebooks, some recent techniques such as pitch prefiltering [6] and

adaptive pulse positioning [1] have attempted to model the non-uniform nature of the FCB pulse distribution.

In this paper, we propose the use of an FCB excitation based on adaptively positioned **windows**. These windows correspond to few, periodically spaced time intervals which contain most of the fixed excitation energy. By allocating most of the FCB bits to these windows, a substantial coding gain can be achieved resulting in enhanced speech quality at low bit-rates.

To efficiently code a window as a single entity, it is important that a window does not extend across two adjacent subframes. However, window locations are dictated by the local speech character, while subframe boundaries are normally fixed and uniformly spaced. To reconcile this contradiction, we allow the subframe and frame sizes to vary in a controlled manner so that each window remains within a single subframe.

The use of adaptive windows is advantageous only for voiced and some transient speech. For all other types of speech frames; i.e., silent, unvoiced, and other transient frames, the energy localization property does not hold, so that it is more appropriate to use conventional FCB coding. Hence, to maximize coding efficiency, our proposal incorporates a frame level classification. Each input frame is classified to one of three classes: voiced, unvoiced, and silence. The classifier also contributes to a mode-dependent rate-determination rule. Following classification, a class-specific encoder is employed.

We have used the proposed model to build a variable-rate speech coder targeted for mobile communication applications. The proposed coder has three externally selectable modes, where each mode offers a different trade-off between average rate and quality.

2. ADAPTIVE WINDOW EXCITATION

2.1. Speech analysis framework

The encoder has a fixed frame structure (**basic frame structure**) for the purpose of performing linear prediction analysis and for packaging the data to be transmitted. Each **basic frame**, which is 160 samples long, is partitioned into two **basic subframes** of length 80 samples each.

Figure 1 shows a block diagram of the encoder. Linear prediction (LP) analysis and open-loop pitch estimation are first performed in each basic frame. The LP parameters are interpolated for the subframes and a residual signal is obtained by filtering the input speech through a linear

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Figure 1. Block diagram of the encoder

prediction whitening filter. This is followed by a modification of the residual signal according to the relaxation CELP (RCELP) model [4]. The RCELP modification uses time-warping to linearize the pitch contour, while simultaneously ensuring that the speech quality is not degraded as a result. Thus, RCELP ensures that a pitch value, which is transmitted once per frame and interpolated linearly for samples within the frame, will suffice to model instantaneous variations in pitch.

2.2. Window Positioning

Following residual modification, the location of the adaptive windows are determined through an analysis of the residual signal. Specifically an energy contour of the modified residual is first obtained; Fig. 2(a) shows a typical energy contour in a voiced segment. Next, the adaptive windows are positioned such that they are evenly spaced, occur once in a pitch period, and cover the most important (high energy) segments of the modified residual as shown in Fig. 2(b). The duration of the windows is dependent on the frame pitch; in practice, windows of length 16 or 24 samples are used.

After determining the window locations, we check to see if the first window position can be predicted from the previous frame. Often, the first window in a frame is approximately one pitch period away from the last window in the previous frame. In such cases, the position prediction error (**jitter**) is encoded and the corresponding frame is referred to as a jittered voiced frame.

In other cases, the first window position may not be easily predictable, and hence, must be encoded independently. We refer to such a frame as a **reset voiced** frame. Note that for both jittered and reset voiced frames, the position of the first window and the pitch period determine the location of the subsequent windows.

Figure 2. Determining window positions. (a) A smoothed energy contour and (b) residual signal with window positions for a typical periodic segment.

It is important to prevent a window from straddling a frame or subframe boundary. For this purpose, we define, corresponding to each basic subframe, a **search subframe**, whose starting and ending points are offset from those of the basic subframe. Thus, while basic subframe j ($j = 0$ or 1) in frame k ($k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) extends from samples $n_{bs} = 160k + 80j$ to $n_{be} = 160k + 80j + 79$, the corresponding search subframe extends from $n_{bs} + d_s$ to $n_{be} + d_e$, where $-\frac{W}{2} \leq d_s, d_e < \frac{W}{2}$. Here, W is the length of the window. The offset values, d_s and d_e , are chosen independently in each subframe such that the search subframe will fully contain windows whose centers are located in the corresponding basic subframe. The two search subframes that correspond to a basic frame together constitute a **search frame**. Note that the search subframe boundaries can be inferred from the window position and sizes; hence they need not be transmitted to the decoder.

We note that search subframes and frames are used for the purpose of determining the optimal FCB and ACB excitation vectors and gains during analysis-by-synthesis. The LPC analysis, pitch extraction, RCELP modification and transmission of the encoded parameters are synchronized with the basic frames.

3. RATE DETERMINATION AND FRAME CLASSIFICATION

3.1. Encoder Mode

The encoder operates in one of three distinct selectable modes. Each mode is characterized by a desired average bit-rate or (equivalently) a desired average speech quality. The encoder mode is selected externally, either in response to a Quality of Service objective or an existing network congestion level. The three modes in our codec and their corresponding average bit-rates in a typical two-way telephone conversation scenario are economy mode (2.3 kbps), standard mode (2.7 kbps) and premium mode (3.4 kbps).

Figure 3. Classification and rate determination

3.2. Frame Classification

Frame classification [3] is an important technique that allows a speech coder to use different coding algorithms, each matched to a phonetically distinct category of speech - thereby maximizing the coding efficiency.

Our proposed codec includes a classifier that maps each input speech frame to a phonetic class (silent, unvoiced, or voiced) and a bit-rate (discussed later). The phonetic class is determined using a multi-layer decision tree (Fig. 3). At the highest layer, a voice activity detection block operates on the input speech and distinguishes silent frames from other frames. At the next layer, the non-silent frames are processed and unvoiced frames are distinguished from voiced ones. The parameters used to make these decisions include short-term energy, peakiness, zero crossing rate, and long-term prediction gain. Note that transient frames are assigned to the voiced class.

3.3. Rate Determination

The rate used to encode a frame is determined by the mode and the phonetic class of the frame. Specifically, frames classified as silent are encoded at 0.8 kbps. Unvoiced frames are allowed either 2 kbps (in the economy or standard modes of operation) or 4 kbps (in the premium mode). Voiced frames may be coded at either 4 or 8.5 kbps, as determined by a mode-dependent classifier. Table 1 shows the relative frequency of the decisions of the frame classifier and the rate determination algorithm in typical two-way communication.

4. EXCITATION CODING AND PARAMETER QUANTIZATION

4.1. Excitation Coding

A key feature in the proposed speech codec is a frame-dependent excitation coder. As mentioned earlier, adaptive windows are appropriate only in strongly periodic and some transient frames. In other cases, a uniform pulse/excitation

Table 1. Classes of frames, associated bit rates, and relative frequency of occurrence in different operation modes.

Class	Bit Rate (kbps)	Relative Frequency (%)		
		Economy	Standard	Premium
Silence	0.8	56.4	56.4	56.4
Unvoiced	2.0	16.1	16.1	0
	4.0	0	0	16.1
Voiced	4.0	18.1	8.9	0
	8.5	9.4	18.6	27.5

distribution is more desirable.

In the proposed speech codec, we employ a random excitation codebook with a uniform temporal distribution of excitation energy in silent and unvoiced frames (at both 2 kbps and 4 kbps). In these cases, no ACB contribution is used.

The adaptive windows approach is used in voiced frames encoded at 4 kbps and 8.5 kbps. At both rates, an ACB contribution is first determined in each search subframe by warping (based on the RCELP model) and optimally scaling the past excitation. Next, an analysis-by-synthesis approach is used to determine the optimal FCB excitation.

At 4 kbps, the FCB contribution is a set of binary pulses (+1 or -1) which are constrained to lie inside the windows. For windows of length 24, three pulses are allowed in each window and for windows of length 16, four pulses are allowed. The pulses are on fixed, interleaved tracks defined inside the windows. One pulse is allowed on each track in all cases. In addition to these constraints, the FCB excitation must be periodic - equivalently all windows within a search subframe are constrained to have the same FCB excitation (relative to the window position). The optimal FCB excitation and the corresponding gain are determined using standard CELP techniques [5].

At 8.5 kbps, the FCB excitation is composed of two components. First, in each search subframe, we choose an FCB excitation and the corresponding gain based on adaptive windows. This excitation is constrained and chosen in a manner that is identical to the 4 kbps case. A second component of the FCB excitation is a set of 8 additional binary valued pulses, each placed on fixed, interleaved tracks that cover the search subframe. Each pulse is allowed (but not constrained) to be periodically repeated. The decision to repeat a pulse or otherwise is a part of the CELP optimization loop. The best combination of these additional pulses and a corresponding subframe-level gain is determined. Note that the two components (adaptive windows and fixed pulses) have independent gains.

The objective of using additional pulses on a grid at 8.5 kbps is two-fold. On one hand, these pulses can effectively handle transients and unusual voiced frames which are not well-suited to the adaptive windows paradigm. On the other hand, when adequate bits are available (as in the premium mode), the additional excitation improves the speech quality.

Table 2. Average bit rates and informal MOS scores obtained for different coding systems.

Coding System	Average Bit Rate (kbps)	MOS Score
TIA/IS-733	7.6	4.07
TIA/IS-127	4.4	3.98
Proposed Codecs:		
Economy Mode	2.3	3.60
Standard Mode	2.7	3.92
Premium Mode	3.4	4.13

4.2. Parameter Quantization

For robust and efficient transmission, the LP coefficients are transformed into line spectral frequencies (LSF). LSF quantization is achieved by the combination of a first order switched moving average (MA) prediction of the LSFs and a multi-stage vector quantizer (VQ). Switched prediction is used only in voiced frames to maximize coding efficiency; elsewhere standard memoryless VQ is used.

A first order MA prediction is used for the FCB gain and the prediction error is jointly vector quantized with the ACB gain. The bit allocation for the LSF and gain parameters is class dependent.

In the decoder, an adaptive postfilter [2] is used to enhance the perceptual quality of the decoded speech. This postprocessing step consists of both long-term and short-term filters in addition to a class-dependent spectral tilt-compensation filter.

5. SUBJECTIVE TEST RESULTS

An informal absolute-category rating mean opinion score (MOS) test was performed to evaluate the subjective quality of the proposed coder in different modes of operation. The test database consists of 6 male and 6 female speech files, each 8 seconds long. The following coding systems were compared: IS-733 (Q13) variable rate speech coder, TIA/IS-127 enhanced variable rate coder (EVRC), and the proposed coder in the economy, standard and premium modes. A panel of 60 impartial listeners were asked to evaluate each file on the MOS scale after listening via head-phone. The order of presentation was randomized.

Table 2 summarizes the results of the MOS test. The difference in scores must be mainly viewed in the light of the coding gains that are achieved. Specifically, our premium mode at 3.4 kbps scores 4.13 in the test compared to IS-733 at 7.6 kbps which scores 4.07. The standard mode score (3.92) is only a small drop from the premium mode's despite the 20% decrease in the average bit-rate. The economy mode coder with an average bit rate of 2.3 kbps, obtains an MOS score of 3.60.

6. CONCLUSION

A novel adaptive windows paradigm for encoding the FCB excitation in CELP speech coders was presented. The approach localizes the non-zero components of the FCB excitation to a set of windows in the subframe. A procedure for determining the location and size of the windows was described. To prevent windows from straddling subframe and frame boundaries, the subframe lengths are altered in

a controlled manner. A class-dependent excitation encoder is used to maximize the benefits of the adaptive windows.

The paradigm was tested on a selectable-mode variable-rate CELP speech coder. Informal listening tests show that speech of very good quality and intelligibility can be obtained over a range of bit rates.

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